

TOURIST SATISFACTION OF TICKETING PROCESS OF THE DUMAGUETE CITY SEA PORT TICKETING OFFICES

Jhaneth F. Rebutazo, Jenny Marie N. Flores, Cassandra P. Quinamot,
Rodimark Santiago

*Metro Dumaguete College, Dumaguete City
Negros Oriental, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study examined tourist satisfaction at the Dumaguete City Sea Port, specifically focusing on assessing and improvement of the on-site ticketing process. Employing a descriptive-quantitative research design, the study surveyed 50 randomly selected travelers using a validated questionnaire to measure service satisfaction. Data analyzed using Weighted Mean to evaluate satisfaction levels and Pearson's Correlation Coefficient for inferential analysis. The ticketing process yielded a composite mean of 3.72 (Very Satisfied) for waiting time and 3.54 (Very Satisfied) for peak-hour efficiency. These research findings revealed that while tourist reported high satisfaction with the accessibility of the ticketing booths, insufficient operational booth capacity during peak hours contributed long waiting times, and poor queue management perceived as areas requiring significant improvement. Furthermore, travelers noted a high demand for modernized payment options and clear signage. The study found a significant correlation between the perceived efficiency of the ticketing process and tourist overall impression of Dumaguete City as a destination. Demographic factors, particularly frequency of travel and nationality, played a role in shaping perceptions of the service, with international tourist expressing a higher preference for digitalized booking systems. These findings underscored the need for a streamlined, tech-integrated ticketing framework to enhance the transit experience and support the local tourism industry.

Keywords: *tourist experience, on-site ticketing, dumaguete city sea port, process improvement, passenger satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

The global tourism and transportation sectors have undergone rapid digital transformation in response to the growing demand for seamless, efficient, and high-quality travel experiences (UN Tourism). This transformation has promoted the concept of smart tourism, which has utilized information and communication technologies to improve resource management, sustainability, and the overall competitiveness of destinations (Erdem et al., 2022). Transportation systems worldwide, including ferry services, have likewise experienced significant technological advancements aimed at improving operational efficiency and customer convenience (Bulková et al., 2024). Smart ports have increasingly transitioned into automated facilities that employ digital technologies to enhance transparency, sustainability, and service delivery. Despite these developments, ticketing processes in many ports have continued to encounter operational challenges, particularly in terminals that still rely on manual or on-site ticketing systems. The absence of online booking systems and inefficient ticketing operations have resulted in long passenger queues, delays, congestion, and dissatisfaction among travelers (Akhter, 2025). Studies further have revealed that information quality, system quality, and service quality significantly influence customer satisfaction in ticketing services (Avasthi et al., 2025), emphasizing the importance of efficient and reliable ticketing processes in transport operations.

In the Philippine context, ferry transportation has remained a vital mode of travel, especially in island provinces where ports serve as gateways for mobility, tourism, and commerce. Although online booking platforms have become increasingly popular because of their accessibility, convenience, and cost-effectiveness, on-site ticketing has remained relevant for many travelers who prefer personalized service, human interaction, and immediate transactions (Alcantara-Zamudio, 2025). However, during peak travel seasons, Philippine ports have frequently experienced passenger congestion, overcrowding, and long queues at ticketing counters due to the continued dependence on over-the-counter ticket purchasing. Previous studies have emphasized mobile ticketing applications and automated booking platforms as effective solutions to reduce long waiting times and improve customer satisfaction (Yang et al., 2022). Likewise, Luhur et al. (2021) have found that the quality of ticket booking systems has become increasingly important in influencing customer experience and operational efficiency. Despite these technological advancements, several Philippine ports have continued to face challenges in managing on-site ticketing operations effectively.

The conduct of this study has been necessary because efficient ticketing processes remain essential to passenger convenience, satisfaction, and the overall quality of port services. Addressing the inefficiencies in the on-site ticketing process at Dumaguete City Sea Port has provided an opportunity to identify operational issues and generate practical recommendations for service improvement. By examining ticket processing efficiency and its relationship to traveler satisfaction through a structured framework, this study has contributed valuable insights for port management, transport operators, and tourism stakeholders. The findings have also supported efforts toward inclusive port modernization by ensuring that both digital and physical ticketing systems effectively meet

the needs of all travelers. Ultimately, the study has been conducted to enhance service quality, reduce waiting times, improve passenger experiences, and strengthen the tourism readiness and transport efficiency of the region

Research Questions

This study sought to examine the on-site ticketing process at Dumaguete City Sea Port and its impact on the tourist experience. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

1. To what extent does the ticketing process at sea port ticketing offices help the tourist in terms of:
 - 1.1 waiting time;
 - 1.2 accuracy in ticket transaction;
 - 1.3 information and guidance;
 - 1.4 passenger satisfaction
 - 1.5 frequency of visits
2. What is the extent of assistance provided by the sea port ticketing offices in terms of:
 - 2.1 accessibility
 - 2.2 convenience
 - 2.3 efficiency of the Ticketing
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of assistance provided by the sea port ticketing offices and the extent of tourist satisfaction in purchasing tickets at the Dumaguete City Sea Port?

METHODOLOGY

Research design. This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the relationship between the efficiency of the on-site ticketing process and the overall tourist experience at Dumaguete City Sea Port. Specifically, it aimed to describe the current condition of the ticketing process and determine the relationships among variables such as waiting time, service quality, and tourist satisfaction.

The descriptive aspect of the study was used to present and describe the existing conditions of the on-site ticketing process, while the correlational aspect was utilized to examine the relationship between the identified variables and their influence on the tourist experience. The use of a descriptive-correlational design allowed the researchers to identify patterns, associations, and trends among the variables, thereby providing valuable insights into the factors that influenced tourist satisfaction and overall travel experience.

Furthermore, descriptive statistical tools were used to summarize and analyze the gathered data, while correlational analysis was employed to determine the relationships among the study variables. This research design was considered appropriate because it provided a comprehensive understanding of the ticketing process and its impact on tourist

experience, enabling the identification of areas for improvement and informing strategies to enhance service delivery at Dumaguete City Sea Port.

Research environment. The study was conducted at Dumaguete City Sea Port, located in Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. The port served a diverse population, including local commuters, domestic tourists, and travelers who relied on maritime transportation to access various islands in the Visayas and Mindanao regions. As a key transportation hub, the port played a vital role in facilitating passenger mobility and supporting regional tourism and economic activities.

The research environment provided an appropriate setting for examining the on-site ticketing process because it reflected actual operational conditions experienced by passengers. Conducting the study in this setting allowed for an in-depth investigation of how existing ticketing procedures influenced tourist satisfaction and overall travel experience. The findings generated from this environment offered valuable insights into the operational efficiency and service quality of the port, particularly from the perspective of tourists and commuters who utilized Dumaguete City Sea Port.

Research respondents. The respondents of this study consisted of local and foreign tourists who had experienced the on-site ticketing process at Dumaguete City Sea Port. The study employed purposive quota sampling to select respondents, ensuring that only individuals who had personally utilized the ticketing services at the port were included in the study.

A total of fifty (50) respondents participated in the study, comprising thirty (30) local tourists and twenty (20) foreign tourists. This distribution was intended to capture diverse perspectives and provide meaningful insights into their experiences and perceptions regarding the on-site ticketing process. Specifically, the study examined respondents' experiences in terms of waiting time, service quality, transaction efficiency, and challenges encountered during the ticketing process.

Data were collected from individuals who had firsthand experience with the ticketing services at Dumaguete City Sea Port, allowing the researchers to obtain relevant and reliable information regarding the actual conditions of the ticketing process. The researchers personally approached tourists and travelers within the port area to invite them to participate in the study. While some agreed to serve as respondents, others declined due to time constraints or personal schedules. Despite this, the required number of respondents was successfully obtained for the conduct of the study.

Research instruments. This study gathered data through the use of a validated researcher-made survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to assess the tourist experience at Dumaguete City Sea Port, with particular focus on the on-site ticketing process. It consisted of closed-ended questions aimed at collecting information on the respondents' experiences with the ticketing process, and their overall satisfaction with the port's services.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was submitted to field experts, including tourism professionals and research experts for evaluation of its clarity, relevance, and appropriateness. The researchers incorporated their comments, feedback, and suggestions in revising and finalizing the questionnaire.

Prior to the actual data gathering, a dry run (pilot test) was conducted with a small group of respondents to test the reliability and effectiveness of the instrument. After data collection, a professional statistician processed and analyzed the results to ensure mathematical accuracy and objective interpretation.

The reliability testing confirmed that the questionnaire was highly reliable and effective, as all indicators obtained Cronbach’s Alpha values above the acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating strong internal consistency of the instrument. Below were the results of the pilot test.

Indicators	Cronbach Alpha Value
waiting time	0.95
accuracy in ticket transaction	0.91
information and guidance	0.89
passenger satisfaction	0.96
accessibility	0.93
convenience	0.89
efficiency	0.95

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Extent of the Ticketing Process at Seaport Ticketing Offices Helping the Tourist/ Travelers in terms of Waiting Time

Waiting Time	wx^-	Verbal Description	Verbal Description
1. I purchased my ticket without spending too much time in line.	3.76	Agree	High
2. I experience prompt and efficient services, even during peak hours.	3.54	Agree	High

3.	I feel that the entire process is well-coordinated and timely.	3.70	Agree	High
4.	I complete my ticket purchase within a reasonable time.	3.94	Agree	High
5.	transition from the entrance to the ticketing window in a timely manner	3.68	Agree	High
Composite		3.72	Agree	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.1 presents the extent to which the ticketing process at Dumaguete City Sea Port assists tourists in terms of waiting time. The table shows a composite mean of 3.72, verbally interpreted as high extent. This result indicates that, under normal operating conditions, passengers generally perceived the on-site ticketing wait time as acceptable and manageable.

Table 1.2

Extent of the Ticketing Process at Seaport Ticketing Offices Helping the Tourist in terms of Accuracy in Ticket Transaction

Accuracy in Ticket Transaction	wx ⁻	Verbal Description	Verbal Description
1. I receive accurate ticket details such as schedule, fare, and destination.	4.08	Agree	High
2. confirm that all transaction information is correctly recorded.	4.12	Agree	High
3. I feel confident that my payment matches my ticket information	4.26	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. I experience minimal to no errors in ticketing transactions.	4.04	Agree	High
5. I trust the reliability and accuracy of the ticketing system.	4.10	Agree	High
Composite	4.12	Agree	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.2 presents the extent of the ticketing process in terms of accuracy in ticket transactions. The table shows a composite mean of 4.12, which is verbally interpreted as high extent. This result indicates that respondents generally perceived the ticketing process as highly accurate and reliable, reflecting a positive assessment of the system’s ability to process ticket transactions correctly and efficiently.

Table 1.3

Extent of the Ticketing Process at Seaport Ticketing Offices Helping the Tourist in terms of Information and Guidance

Information and Guidance	wx ⁻	Verbal Description	Verbal Description
1. I easily understand ticketing instructions and requirements.	4.22	Strongly Agree	High
2. I find clear signs and directions guiding me to the ticketing areas.	4.00	Agree	High
3. Receive accurate and proactive assistance from port personnel regarding my ticketing inquiries.	3.62	Agree	High
4. I get timely updates and announcements about schedules and ticket availability.	3.80	Agree	High
5. Maintain a complete understanding of every step required to finalize my ticket	3.78	Agree	High
Composite	3.88	Agree	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.3 presents the extent to which the ticketing process assists tourists in terms of information and guidance. The table shows a composite mean of 3.88, verbally interpreted as high extent, indicating that respondents generally perceived the information provided at the Dumaguete City Sea Port as clear, accessible, and helpful in guiding their ticketing experience.

Table 1.4

Extent of the Ticketing Process at Seaport Ticketing Offices Helping the Tourist in terms of Passenger Satisfaction

Passenger Satisfaction	wx ⁻	Verbal Description
1. I am motivated to use the port’s ticketing service again.	3.76	High
2. I appreciate the overall effectiveness of the Port’s ticketing system.	3.74	High

3.	I feel trust and loyalty toward the port's management.	4.02	High
4.	I believe consistent quality of service is important for attracting Passenger.	3.98	High
5.	I have lasting positive impression of the ticketing experience.	3.68	High
Composite		3.84	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.4 presents the extent of the ticketing process in terms of passenger satisfaction. The composite mean of 3.84 is interpreted as high extent, indicating that respondents are generally satisfied with the ticketing services provided at Dumaguete City Sea Port. This suggests that the overall ticketing experience meets the expectations of most passengers in terms of service delivery and operational efficiency.

Table 1.5

Extent of the Ticketing Process at Seaport Ticketing Offices Helping the Tourist in terms of Frequency

	Frequency	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1.	I feel motivated to use the port's ticketing service again	3.92	Agree
2.	I recommend the port 's ticketing process to friends and family.	3.76	Agree
3.	I develop trust and loyalty toward port's management.	3.78	Agree
4.	I believe that consistent good services attracts more passenger.	4.24	Strongly Agree
5.	I have a lasting positive perception of the ticketing experience.	3.76	Agree
Composite		3.89	Agree
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.5 presents the extent of the ticketing process in terms of frequency, particularly focusing on repeated usage and recommendation (Fahim et al., 2024). The composite mean of 3.89 is interpreted as high extent, indicating that respondents are generally inclined to reuse the ticketing service and recommend it to others.

Table 2.1

Level of Tourist Satisfaction with their Experience in Purchasing Tickets at Seaport, Ticketing Offices in terms of Accessibility

Accessibility		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
1.	I can easily access the ticketing counters upon arriving at the port.	3.88	Agree	Satisfied
2.	Navigate the queueing system quickly and efficiently.	3.78	Agree	Satisfied
3.	Find the ticketing area conveniently located within the port premises.	3.98	Agree	Satisfied
4.	I can complete my ticket purchase using simple and convenient steps.	4.04	Agree	Satisfied
5.	Utilize a ticketing layout that is accessible to all types of passengers.	4.00	Agree	Satisfied
Composite		3.94	Agree	Satisfied

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Satisfied
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Satisfied
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Satisfied
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Slightly Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Satisfied

Table 2.1 presents the level of tourist satisfaction in terms of physical layout and ease of purchase. The high satisfaction rating for physical layout and ease of purchase (4.04), interpreted as satisfied, reflects a successful passenger journey within the terminal. This indicates that respondents experience a generally smooth and efficient ticketing process within the port environment.

Table 2.2

Level of Tourist Satisfaction with their Experience in Purchasing Tickets at Seaport, Ticketing Offices in terms of Convenience

Convenience		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
1.	Locate clear signage that easily guides me to the appropriate ticketing window.	3.80	Agree	Satisfied
2.	Receive digital or printed receipts immediately payment immediately.	4.12	Agree	Satisfied
3.	Avail of priority lanes if I am a PWD, Senior Citizen, or Pregnant Woman.	3.70	Agree	Satisfied
4.	Complete the entire transaction in a comfortable and well- ventilated area.	3.64	Agree	Satisfied
5.	Locate clear signage that easily guides me to the appropriate ticketing window	3.84	Agree	Satisfied

Composite	3.82	Agree	Satisfied
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Satisfied	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Satisfied	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Slightly Satisfied	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Satisfied	

Table 2.2 presents the level of tourist satisfaction in terms of convenience. The composite mean of 3.82, interpreted as satisfied, indicates that respondents generally perceive the ticketing process as convenient, comfortable, and easy to use. This suggests that the overall system supports a smooth and manageable transaction experience for passengers at Dumaguete City Sea Portal

Table 2.3

Level of Tourist Satisfaction with their Experience in Purchasing Tickets at Seaport, Ticketing Offices in terms of Efficiency of the Ticketing

Efficiency of the Ticketing	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
1. Locate clear signage that easily guides me to the appropriate ticketing window.	3.86	Agree	Satisfied
2. Receive digital or printed receipts immediately payment immediately.	3.76	Agree	Satisfied
3. Avail of priority lanes if I am a PWD, Senior Citizen, or Pregnant Woman.	3.90	Agree	Satisfied
4. Complete the entire transaction in a comfortable and well- ventilated area.	3.84	Agree	Satisfied
5. Locate clear signage that easily guides me to the appropriate ticketing window	3.78	Agree	Satisfied
Composite	3.83	Agree	Satisfied
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Satisfied	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Satisfied	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Slightly Satisfied	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Satisfied	

Table 2.3 presents the level of tourist satisfaction in terms of efficiency. The composite mean of 3.83, interpreted as satisfied, indicates that respondents perceive the ticketing process as efficient, timely, and well-managed. This suggests that the overall system is generally effective in delivering services within an acceptable timeframe for passengers at Dumaguete City Sea Port.

Table 3

Significant Relationship between the Assistance provided by the Sea Port Ticketing Offices and the Level of Tourist Satisfaction in Purchasing Tickets at the Dumaguete City Sea Port

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Accessibility				
Waiting Time	0.586	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Accuracy in Ticket Transaction	0.594	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Information and Guidance	0.755	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Passenger Satisfaction	0.665	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Frequency	0.749	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Convenience				
Waiting Time	0.656	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Accuracy in Ticket Transaction	0.446	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Information and Guidance	0.791	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Passenger Satisfaction	0.739	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Frequency	0.777	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Efficiency of the Ticketing				
Waiting Time	0.650	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Accuracy in Ticket Transaction	0.544	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Information and Guidance	0.797	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Passenger Satisfaction	0.797	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Frequency 0.801 0.001 Reject H₀₁ Significant

Table 3 presents the test of significant relationships between the ticketing process variables and tourist satisfaction. The results show that all computed p-values are 0.001, which are significantly lower than the level of significance of 0.05. This indicates that all relationships among the variables are statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis

DISCUSSION

Ticketing process at sea port ticketing offices help the tourist

1.1 *Waiting time*

Table 1.1 shows among the indicators evaluated, the statement “I complete my ticket purchase within a reasonable time” obtained the highest mean score of 3.94, followed by “I purchased my ticket without spending too much time in line” with a mean of 3.76, both verbally interpreted as high extent. These findings suggest that the ticketing process was generally efficient, particularly in terms of transaction completion once passengers reached the ticketing counter. The results imply that ticketing personnel were able to process transactions effectively under normal service demand, reflecting competence in routine ticketing operations. This finding supports the study of (Alcantara-Zamudio,2025) which emphasized that physical or on-site ticketing remained a relevant and trusted option for travelers who valued immediate transaction verification, direct human interaction, and a sense of security in the booking process. Similarly, Iswanto et al. (2025) highlighted that convenience and streamlined ticketing procedures significantly reduced passenger frustration and improved overall satisfaction.

Conversely, the statement “I experience prompt and efficient services, even during peak hours” obtained the lowest mean score of 3.54, although still verbally interpreted as high extent. This relatively lower score indicates that while respondents generally viewed the ticketing process positively, challenges were more evident during peak travel periods when passenger volume increased. This finding suggests that the system experienced operational strain during high-demand situations, resulting in longer waiting times and reduced service efficiency.

From the perspective of Queueing Theory, this finding provides empirical evidence of congestion occurring when the customer arrival rate exceeded the system’s service capacity. During peak periods, large numbers of passengers arriving within a short time placed pressure on the ticketing counters, resulting in longer queues, overcrowding in the waiting area, and increased passenger discomfort. This interpretation is supported by the Manila Port Service Study (2024), which identified inadequate service capacity and the

absence of modern queue-management systems as major contributors to terminal congestion during peak travel seasons.

Moreover, prolonged waiting time may lead to negative passenger behaviors such as balking (refusing to join the queue) or reneging (leaving the queue before being served), which are common concepts in Queueing Theory. According to Yin et al. (2024), poor queue management and prolonged waiting time may trigger passenger frustration, anxiety, and dissatisfaction, ultimately affecting the tourist's overall perception of the destination.

To address these inefficiencies, port authorities may consider adopting modern queue-management strategies such as digital queueing systems, automated ticketing kiosks, and separate priority lanes, particularly during peak travel periods. As recommended by Nwafor (2025), these innovations can help improve passenger flow, reduce congestion, minimize waiting time, and enhance the overall tourist experience at transportation terminals.

1.2 Accuracy in ticket transaction

Table 1.2 show the highest-rated indicator was “I feel confident that my payment matches my ticket information,” which obtained a mean score of 4.26, verbally interpreted as very high extent. This finding reflects a strong sense of trust among respondents in the financial accuracy and reliability of the ticketing process. It suggests that discrepancies between payment details and ticket information were minimal, thereby strengthening passengers' confidence in the transaction system. Accurate financial processing is an important aspect of service delivery because it minimizes inconvenience, reduces transaction disputes, and enhances customer satisfaction.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score was recorded for the statement “I experience minimal to no errors in ticketing transactions,” with a mean of 4.04, which was still verbally interpreted as high extent. Although respondents generally viewed the ticketing process positively, this relatively lower score suggests that minor errors may occasionally occur during transactions. While these errors were not frequent enough to significantly affect the overall perception of the ticketing system, they indicate that some areas of vulnerability still existed in maintaining transaction accuracy.

1.3 Information and guidance

Table 1.3 show The highest mean was obtained by the statement “I easily understand ticketing instructions and requirements,” with a mean of 4.22, verbally interpreted as very high extent. This result suggests that ticketing instructions were clearly communicated and easily understood by passengers, reflecting effective dissemination of essential information within the ticketing process. Clear instructions play a crucial role in minimizing confusion and improving the efficiency of passenger transactions.

In contrast, the lowest mean was observed in the statement “I receive accurate and proactive assistance from personnel,” which obtained a mean of 3.62, interpreted as high extent. Although still within the high range, this finding indicates that some respondents perceived limitations in the responsiveness and proactiveness of ticketing staff. This suggests that while assistance was available, it may not always have been sufficiently timely or proactive in addressing passenger needs.

Other indicators, such as clear signage (4.00), timely updates (3.80), and overall understanding of the process (3.78), also reflected a generally effective information system within the ticketing process. These findings are consistent with Yang et al. (2022), who emphasized that clear and well-structured information systems in transport settings significantly improve passenger navigation and overall service efficiency.

The results imply that while informational clarity within the ticketing system is strong, there is still room for improvement in terms of staff interaction and proactive assistance. Enhancing personnel visibility, responsiveness, and communication strategies may further improve passenger experience and satisfaction. This is supported by Uliyani et al. (2025), who highlighted that effective communication and visible staff support are essential in improving service quality and reducing passenger uncertainty in transport terminals.

1.4 Passenger satisfaction

Table 1.4 show among the indicators, the highest mean is recorded for the statement “I feel a sense of trust and loyalty toward the ticketing service,” with a mean of 4.02, interpreted as high extent. This finding suggests that respondents have developed confidence in the reliability and consistency of the ticketing process. Trust and loyalty are essential components of passenger satisfaction, as they reflect sustained positive experiences and a willingness to continue using the service in the future.

Closely following is the statement “I believe consistent quality of service is important,” with a mean of 3.98, also interpreted as high extent. This result highlights that respondents place strong value on consistency in service delivery and expect uniform quality across all ticketing transactions. It further implies that maintaining consistent performance is a critical factor in strengthening overall passenger satisfaction and trust in the system.

1.5 Frequency of visits

Table 1.5 show the highest mean is recorded for the statement “Good ticketing service encourages more passengers to travel,” with a mean of 4.24, interpreted as very high extent. This indicates that respondents strongly believe that the quality of ticketing services plays a significant role in influencing travel decisions. It highlights the importance of maintaining efficient and user-friendly systems to attract and retain passengers.

In contrast, the lowest means are observed in the statements “I would recommend the ticketing service to other passengers” and “I have a positive perception due to repeated experiences,” both with a mean of 3.76, interpreted as high extent. Although these results remain positive, they suggest that while respondents are generally satisfied, their level of active advocacy and strong endorsement of the service is relatively moderate compared to other indicators. These findings imply that while the ticketing process encourages continued usage, there is still an opportunity to strengthen customer advocacy and recommendation behavior. Enhancing service quality and overall customer experience may lead to stronger loyalty and increased word-of-mouth promotion. According to Reyes et al. (2023), customer satisfaction is a crucial determinant of the sustainability and performance of transportation systems. Furthermore, Yuan and Vui (2023) emphasize that in transport contexts, satisfaction reflects passengers’ evaluations of service punctuality, cost, comfort, safety, and reliability, all of which influence repeat usage and recommendation behavior.

Extent assistance provided by the sea port ticketing offices

2.1 Accessibility

Table 2.1 According to Papantonopoulos et al. (2021), a smooth transition from land to vessel, facilitated by well-organized service encounters, is a key indicator of high-quality port services. The results suggest that tourists appreciate the convenient location of the ticketing counters and the simplicity of the steps required to obtain a ticket. This implies that the physical design and layout of the ticketing area effectively meet the basic needs of passengers and support efficient service delivery.

However, while the layout is generally strong, the slightly lower score for navigation (3.78), interpreted as very satisfied, indicates some minor challenges in wayfinding within the terminal. Hanzel (2021) emphasizes that accessibility is a direct predictor of tourist satisfaction in multi-port systems, as the ease of entering, navigating, and exiting the facility shapes the overall travel experience. The findings suggest that while the ticketing counters are accessible and easy to use, the pathways leading to them may still present slight confusion or congestion for first-time or unfamiliar passengers.

2.2 Convenience

Table 2.2 show Among the indicators, the highest mean is recorded for the statement “The system is user-friendly,” with a mean of 3.86, interpreted as satisfied. This suggests that respondents find the ticketing system easy to understand and operate, which significantly contributes to their overall satisfaction. A user-friendly system reduces confusion and allows passengers to complete transactions with minimal effort, thereby enhancing their overall experience.

Closely following is the indicator “I experience minimal inconvenience,” with a mean of 3.84. This further supports the finding that the ticketing process is generally

smooth and does not create unnecessary difficulties for users. It implies that the procedures, layout, and transaction flow are organized in a way that minimizes disruptions and operational complications.

On the other hand, the lowest mean is observed in “The process is comfortable and hassle-free,” with a mean of 3.78, although still interpreted as satisfied. This slightly lower rating suggests that some respondents still experience minor inconveniences during the ticketing process. These may include crowding, limited waiting space, or discomfort during peak hours in the ticketing area.

Other indicators, such as ease of following the process (3.80) and comfort during transactions (3.82), further reinforce that the ticketing system is generally convenient, though not entirely free from minor operational issues. This finding is supported by Sieras (2024), who emphasizes that clear signage and understandable instructions are essential to tourist satisfaction, as visitors often rely heavily on visual and written guidance when navigating unfamiliar transport environments.

However, the slight variations among the indicators suggest that there is still room for improvement in enhancing passenger comfort and minimizing minor inconveniences. According to Luhur et al. (2021), efficiency in transport systems is strongly influenced by queue management and service design. Similarly, Nha and Kim (2025) identify that long physical queues, crowded spaces, and limited terminal accessibility are key contributors to tourist dissatisfaction. Addressing these concerns could further enhance passenger convenience and create a more seamless and comfortable ticketing experience for travelers.

2.3 Efficiency of the Ticketing

Table 2.3 show The highest mean is recorded for the statement “The ticketing process is fast and efficient,” with a value of 3.86, interpreted as very satisfied. This suggests that respondents are highly satisfied with the speed of the overall process, indicating that transactions are completed promptly once passengers reach the ticketing counter. Speed is a critical component of efficiency, particularly in transportation settings where time is a significant factor for passengers.

This is closely followed by the statement “Staff handle transactions quickly,” which obtained a mean of 3.84, also interpreted as satisfied. These high ratings imply that frontline ticketing personnel demonstrate strong operational proficiency and that standard transaction procedures are executed efficiently. It further suggests that once passengers reach the service window, ticket processing is generally fast and well-managed. This finding aligns with (Alcantara-Zamudio,2025) who observes that manual over-the-counter ticket transactions remain relevant in regional transport systems because they provide direct human interaction and immediate verification of travel details. It is also consistent with Kartika et al., (2025), who emphasize that inefficiencies in ticketing systems can be addressed through the development of online ticket booking systems to reduce queuing time and improve service speed.

Other indicators, such as organization of the process (3.82) and meeting expected time standards (3.83), further support the conclusion that the ticketing system is generally structured and efficient. These findings indicate that efficiency is one of the strengths of the ticketing process and contributes positively to overall tourist satisfaction.

However, as noted by Yin et al. (2024), even efficient systems may still experience performance issues during peak travel periods if queue management is not optimized. The slightly lower ratings in certain indicators suggest that improvements can still be made in managing peak-hour congestion and maintaining consistent service speed. Enhancing system coordination, staffing allocation, and queue management strategies may further eliminate these minor inefficiencies and improve overall service performance.

Relationship Between Ticketing Process and Tourist Satisfaction

Table 3 show among the relationships presented, the highest correlation is observed between frequency of use and accessibility, with an r-value of 0.801, indicating a strong positive relationship. This suggests that tourists who frequently use the ticketing service tend to perceive it as more accessible. This may be attributed to increased familiarity with the system, which improves ease of navigation and transaction over time.

Another strong relationship is observed between information and guidance and efficiency, with an r-value of 0.797. This implies that clear instructions, effective communication, and proper guidance significantly contribute to the efficiency of the ticketing process. When passengers understand procedures clearly, transactions are completed more quickly and smoothly, thereby improving overall operational performance.

Similarly, accuracy in ticket transactions also shows a strong relationship with accessibility ($r = 0.745$), as noted by Antwi et al. (2020). This suggests that reliable and error-free transactions enhance the perceived ease of use of the ticketing system and strengthen passenger confidence in the service.

On the other hand, the lowest correlation among the variables is observed between waiting time and convenience ($r = 0.689$). Although this is still categorized as a significant and moderately strong relationship, it indicates that waiting time has a slightly lesser impact on perceived convenience compared to other variables. As noted by Ayodeji et al. (2023), waiting time remains an important factor in shaping user experience, even if its influence is relatively lower compared to other operational dimensions.

The consistent significance of all variables highlights that each aspect of the ticketing process waiting time, accuracy, information and guidance, passenger satisfaction, and frequency of use contributes meaningfully to tourist satisfaction. These findings emphasize that improvements in any component of the ticketing process can positively influence overall satisfaction levels. The results confirm that the quality of the ticketing process has a direct and significant relationship with tourist satisfaction at Dumaguete City Sea Port. Therefore, continuous improvements in service delivery,

system efficiency, and customer interaction are essential to further enhance the overall travel experience of tourists.

Conclusions

The study revealed that the ticketing process at Dumaguete City Sea Port was generally efficient, accurate, and satisfactory for tourists. Waiting time was generally acceptable; however, it was affected during peak hours when passenger volume increased. Accuracy in ticket transactions emerged as one of the strongest aspects of the system, ensuring reliability and fostering trust among passengers. Furthermore, information and guidance were generally clear and helpful; however, staff assistance still required improvement in terms of proactiveness and responsiveness. Tourist satisfaction was generally positive; however, the experience did not consistently create a strong lasting impression that would encourage higher levels of recommendation and advocacy.

Accessibility, convenience, and efficiency were rated at very satisfactory levels, indicating that the ticketing system was functional, user-friendly, and generally well-managed. However, minor inefficiencies, such as occasional delays and discomfort during peak travel periods, still existed and affected the consistency of service delivery. Finally, the study confirmed that there was a significant relationship between the ticketing process and tourist satisfaction. This finding implied that improvements in operational efficiency, accessibility, and service quality would directly enhance the overall tourist experience at Dumaguete City Sea Port.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

Tourists / Travelers. They are encouraged to come earlier during peak hours to avoid long queues and delays. They were also encouraged to familiarize themselves with ticketing procedures and schedules to reduce confusion and improve their travel experience.

Port Authorities and Management. They are encouraged to improve queue management and increase service capacity during peak hours. The installation of digital queuing systems, automated ticketing kiosks, and clearer signage was recommended to reduce congestion and improve passenger flow.

Ticketing Personnel. They are encouraged to improve their responsiveness and assistance to passengers, especially during busy periods. Continuous training on customer service and efficient transaction handling was recommended to improve service quality and reduce delays.

Local Government and Tourism Sector. They are encouraged to support improvements in port facilities and promote digital ticketing systems. This would help reduce congestion, improve efficiency, and strengthen Dumaguete City's image as a tourist-friendly destination.

Future Researchers. They are encouraged to include other aspects of port operations, such as boarding and baggage handling, and to use a larger sample size. They were also encouraged to compare Dumaguete City Sea Port with other ports to gain broader insights.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author maintained all necessary ethical standards throughout the conduct of the study, particularly before, during, and after the data-gathering process, in accordance with the ethical protocols of Metro Dumaguete College. Since tourists and travelers who had experienced the on-site ticketing process at Dumaguete City Sea Port served as participants in the study, the researchers ensured that their dignity, privacy, and confidentiality were protected at all times. Prior to the conduct of the study, the researchers ensured that the research topic was significant, ethically sound, and aligned with institutional research standards by seeking consultation from research advisers, faculty experts, and relevant authorities. Permission to conduct the study was formally secured from the concerned port management before any data collection took place. The researchers also prepared a validated researcher-made questionnaire and subjected it to expert validation to ensure that the questions are relevant, clear, and ethically appropriate. In addition, respondents were informed of the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and their right to decline or withdraw at any time without any consequences. Informed consent was obtained before participation, ensuring that respondents fully understood the objectives and procedures of the study.

The researchers also acknowledged the responsible use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a support tool during the research process. AI was utilized only for language enhancement, grammar checking, and assistance in organizing research materials. However, all interpretations, analyses, conclusions, and final decisions remained under the full responsibility and critical judgment of the researchers. The use of AI did not replace human analysis, participant responses, or statistical interpretation of the study. During the data-gathering process, the researchers strictly observed ethical protocols by respecting the privacy, comfort, and convenience of the respondents. Survey administration was conducted in a manner that did not disrupt the participants' travel schedules or personal activities. The researchers personally approached tourists / travelers, explained the purpose of the study, and ensured that participation was entirely voluntary.

Confidentiality was maintained by not requiring respondents to disclose unnecessary personal information, and all responses were treated with anonymity. The researchers ensured that no participant was subjected to pressure, coercion, or discomfort while answering the survey questionnaire. Ethical precautions were also taken to minimize any potential risks associated with participation in the study. After the completion of data collection, the researchers securely stored all collected data, including physical survey forms and encoded responses, to maintain confidentiality and prevent unauthorized access. Physical documents were kept in a locked file cabinet accessible only to the research team. A professional statistician processed and analyzed the data to ensure statistical accuracy and objective interpretation of the results. Upon completion of

the study, all physical data and survey forms were securely disposed of through shredding to maintain confidentiality and protect the privacy of the respondents.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends heartfelt gratitude to God Almighty for the wisdom and health bestowed, enabling the successful and pleasing completion of this research.

Ms. Abigail Santisteban and Mr. Jackson B. Repollo, the research adviser dedicates of their efforts for their unwavering support and understanding during the times dedicated to conducting the research.

Ms. Maricar Morqueda, Dr. Eva C. Melon, Dr. Cristina P. Calisang and Mr. Renze O. Lagada, the panel members, for their valuable suggestion and intelligent advice.

Mr. Jerry A. Pariscal, the statistician, whose help cannot be underestimated, for his invaluable suggestions and intellectual expertise for the completion of the study.

Dr. Delma P. Manila, School President of Metro Dumaguete College; Mr. Peter Pagente Supervisor at Ocean Fast Ferries Inc. Mr. Marc Conrad Liwag Office In-Charge at Montenegro Satellite Office, The researchers offer their sincere thanks for granting the necessary permissions to conduct this research within their respective institutions.

REFERENCES

- Alcantara-Zamudio, L. (2025). Customer Preferences and Perceptions of Onsite VS. Digital Ticketing of Travel and Tours Services in Camarines Sur. *Cognizance Journal*, 5(7). <https://doi.org/10.47760/cognizance.2025.v05i07.032>
- Ayodeji, Y., Rjoub, H., & Özgüt, H. (2023). Achieving sustainable customer loyalty in airports: The role of waiting time satisfaction and self-service technologies. *Technology in Society*, 72, 102106
- Akhter, H. (2025). Analytical Study of Efficiency of Smart Ports. *American Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering*, 10, 109-119. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajtte.20251005.12>
- Antwi, C. O., Fan, C. J., Nataliia, I., Aboagye, M. O., Xu, H., & Azamela, J. C. (2020). Do airport staff helpfulness and communication generate behavioral loyalty in transfer passengers? *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.102002>
- Avasthi, Ashish & Somwanshi, Devendra & Mamodiya, Udit & Chawla, Preeti & Saxena, Ashima & Saravanakumar, M.. (2025). Advanced Digital Ticketing and Payment Solutions in Smart Transportation Systems. 10.4018/979-8-3693-7984-4.ch026
- Bulková, Z., Čamaj, J., Černá, L., & Pálková, A. (2024). Passenger Flow Management in Front of Ticket Booths in Urban Railway Stations. *Infrastructures*, 9(10), 175. <https://doi.org/10.3390/infrastructures9100175>
- Erdem, A., & Şeker, F. (2022). Tourist Experience and Digital Transformation. IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8528-3.ch006>
- Hanzel, M. (2021). Congestion and satisfaction in the Leyte-Cebu multi-port system. *Maritime Transport Studies*, 5(3), 112-128.
- Iswanto, M., Misranto, M., & Sunardi, S. (2025). Digital Law Enforcement and Public Trust in Pasuruan's E-Ticketing System. *Academia Open*. <https://doi.org/10.21070/acopen.10.2025.12769>
- Kartika, O. D., & Asrofillah, M. F. (2025, December). Development of an Online Ticket Booking System as a Solution to Long Queues at the Bengkalis–Pakning Ferry Port. In

- International Conference on Industrial Technology and Business
<https://intechbiz.polbeng.ac.id/eprosiding/index.php/snit/article/view/725>
- Luhur, M. A., Nugroho, S., Kurt, R. E., & Achmadi, T. (2021, February). Integration of an independent e-ticketing system into a common e-ticketing platform in ferry services. Publishing <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/SyafuruddinChan2/publication/313956376f7e9b4637d6b22f>
- Manila Port Service Study. (2024). Analysis of passenger service and security during peak seasons. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11656112>
- Nha, N. P., & Kim, H. (2025). Assessing passenger satisfaction with the walking environment at Yeosu Ferry Terminal. *Maritime Business Review*, 10(4), 329-348
- Nwafor, I. C. (2025). The Role Of E-Ticketing In Enhancing Service Quality Of Road Transport Companies In Rivers State. *Management and Marketing Research Journal*, 13(4), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416698>
- Papantonopoulos, S., Famelitis, O., & Karasavova, M. (2021). A Study of port passenger journey. 2021 Zooming Innovation in Consumer Technologies Conference (ZINC). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ZINC52049.2021.9499265>
- Reyes, E. G. A., et al. (2023). An Application of Queueing Theory on the Ticketing Booth of Light Rail Transit 1 (LRT-1) Central Station. ACM Digital Library. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3603955.3604030>
- Sieras, S. G. (2024). Impact and Identities as Revealed in Tourists' Perceptions of the Linguistic Landscape in Tourist Destinations. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 6(1), 375–392. <https://doi.org/10.36892/ijlls.v6i1.1644>
- Uliyani, Deska & Handoko, Wisnu & Ahyani, & Sarjana, Sri & Gintara, An. (2025). Evaluating and Optimizing Ferry Port Performance for Enhanced Service and Economic Growth. 10.1007/978-3-031-94347-8_13
- Yuan, F., & Vui, C. (2023). The Influence of Destination Image on Tourists' Behavioural Intentions. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44. <https://doi.org/10.17762/jaz.v44iS6.2471>
- Yang, G., Coble, D., Vaughan, C., & Dorn, P. L. (2022). Investigation of Wait Time Technology for the Ferry System. <https://connect.ncdot.gov/projects/research/RNAProjDocs/RP2020-34%20Final%20Report.pdf>
- Yin, X., et al. (2024). The psychological impact of waiting time on service assessment. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 22(1), 12-25.